

Integrating Energy Reduction and Biodiversity Conservation: A Systems-Based Approach to Sustainable Military Land Management

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Abstract

Use of land by the armed forces is often associated with landscape damage that can be devastating for both plants and animals, and bring long-term consequences for biodiversity. However, in peacetime, military land management can support endangered species, sometimes surpassing conservation outcomes on civilian lands. The United States Air Force (USAF), through its energy and biodiversity management strategies, is reducing its carbon emissions through renewable energy initiatives, while also attempting to offset the ecological consequences of military activities on flora and fauna. But there are considerable challenges for integrating renewable energy technologies, such as solar and wind, into military infrastructure, especially in the face of rapid policy shifts. Critical research gaps in this field include the lack of integrated models linking energy use, emissions, and biodiversity, and the need for more objective, comparative studies between military and non-military lands. A systems-engineering approach to defense sustainability could bridge the currently disconnected literatures on energy efficiency and biodiversity conservation.

Introduction

The US military is the single largest consumer of fuel in the United States. In 2013, it spent almost \$15 billion on energy, using around 90 million barrels of oil (Burke,

2014). Two thirds of all fuel used by the military is consumed by the Air Force (USAF), 84% of which is used by aviation, 12% by facilities and 4% by vehicle and ground equipment (US Air Force, 2010). In 2010, the US Airforce (USAF) released its Air Force Energy Plan, which includes targets for Space Force. The plan outlined steps for energy reduction, including a number of End State Goals, which it aims to meet by 2030 (US Air Force, 2013).

The military can have a positive impact on the environment too, though. Military land management plays a pivotal role in balancing operational readiness and environmental stewardship. Some military bases provide critical habitats for endangered species and plants, while implementing renewable energy initiatives to reduce the USAF's carbon footprint.

Nevertheless, use of land by the armed forces is associated, in the minds of many, with landscape damage that can be devastating for both plants and animals, and bring long-term consequences for biodiversity. The US military's use of Agent Orange as a herbicide in the Vietnam War defoliated 14 per cent of Vietnam's forests and more than half of its mangroves (Hanson et al., 2009). The US also killed Asian elephants in Vietnam, believing they were transporting supplies for enemy forces (Vuong, Nguyen, and La, 2024).

More recent conflicts in Africa and Asia have also had negative impacts on flora and fauna, indirectly, as displaced civilians are forced to hunt bush meat that would normally be protected, or chop down large numbers of trees for firewood around refugee camps, causing deforestation (Hanson et al., 2009). The Democratic

Republic of Congo, which has seen series of armed conflicts since the mid-1990s, has suffered huge losses to its wildlife populations. This has affected fauna large and small, from tiny rodents to gorillas and elephants (Vuong, Nguyen, and La, 2024).

However, use of land by militaries for peacetime training can be quite a different story. Urbanisation, the world over, has seen many species endangered, or even driven to extinction, as vital habitats disappear. Yet the armed forces' dependence on natural terrain to train in has ensured that virtually undisturbed native habitat survives in areas where it would not otherwise (Warren et al., 2007). The growth of the human population sees more greenfield sites lost each year to housing and industry, while intensive agricultural practices see native species fighting against crops for space and being reduced in number through the use of pesticides and herbicides (IPCC 2022). This has seen some natural varieties and breeds of domesticated plants and animals eradicated altogether. This reduction in diversity – including genetic diversity within species – threatens global food security, as crops and livestock become more vulnerable to pests, disease and climate change (IPCC 2022).

1.1 Biodiversity on Military Bases

The vast tracks of land owned by the DoD in the USA have had many conservation successes, as have military bases in other countries, including the UK where RAF Lakenheath and RAF Feltwell are located. In the UK, chalk grasslands – home to particularly rich flora and fauna, and often associated with high densities of butterflies – have been fast disappearing over the last 300 years, having been turned

into agricultural land. Most remaining chalk grassland is found on slopes too steep to farm and military training grounds (Hirst, Pywell and Putwain, 2000).

In the US, there are more than three times the number of Endangered Species Act status species and imperilled species on land owned by the military per 100,000 hectares than on land owned by other agencies (Stein, Scott and Benton, 2008). In Hawaii, the figures are even more impressive with more than a third of all endangered species residing on military lands in Hawaii (Stein, Scott and Benton, 2008). The researchers who came up with these figures found that “although conflicts sometimes exist between the military’s use of these lands and protection of endangered species, the two have found a balanced coexistence at a growing number of installations” (Stein, Scott, Benton, 2008 p.346). However, the scope of the project, funded by the USA’s DoD Legacy Resource Management Program was limited, as it was centred around comparing military land to land owned by other US agencies, ignoring private land. Comparisons with nearby non-military land, including wilderness and urban areas, would have given more meaningful data.

1.1.1 Training in Harmony with Nature

The DoD has had a Natural Resources Program, that aims to ensure the long-term sustainability of the natural landscape on military land, since 1997. Individual installations are required to create integrated natural resources management plans, which balance conservation with mission activities and are delivered by natural resources managers (Stein, 2008). However, these do not always provide full information on the state of biodiversity on installations (Pettus, 2017).

A guide that was written to help natural resources managers on military bases is now into its third edition – *Conserving Biodiversity on Military Lands: A Guide for Natural Resource Managers* (Benton, Ripley and Powledge, 2021). Its authors argue that the DoD is a leader in compliance with natural resources legislation such as the Endangered Species Act, the Clean Water Act and the Migratory Bird Treaty Act, and many others. The US military has carried out extensive biological inventories of its lands, primarily because its military bases are home to the highest density of nationally threatened and endangered species of any federal land management agency.

Although undisturbed wilderness is more often associated with army training than that of air forces, three of the top 10 military facilities in the USA that accommodate a high number of endangered species are air bases – the Eglin Air Force Base and Avon Park Air Force Range in Florida and Vandenberg Air Force Base in California (Stein, Scott, Benton 2008), see Table 4.1. Eglin is home not only to rare and threatened species, including the red-cockaded woodpecker and a fish called the Okaloosa darter, it also hosts less rare wildlife, including deer, wild boar and turkey (Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission, n.d.). Vandenberg has one of the highest concentrations of endangered species in the USA (Hill, 2015).

One frequently cited success story that demonstrates the US Air Force's ability to restore scarce habitat for endangered species, in a landscape that also allows for military manoeuvres to be carried out, involves the restoration of a longleaf pine forest at Eglin. Longleaf pine forest once took up more than 36 million hectares of land in the USA's eastern coastal plain. By 1992, this had shrunk to just 2,000

hectares (Biondo, 1997). The 18,855-hectare Eglin Air Force Base in the Florida panhandle is situated on land that was once dominated by old-growth longleaf pine (Coates et al., 2011). The longleaf pine that had remained since before 1993 was accompanied by an understory of oak trees making it difficult for the pines to reproduce. A 1993 joint initiative by the US Air Force and the Nature Conservancy saw the base begin a conservation plan to restore the longleaf pines. Other pine species were removed, 3 million longleaf pine seedlings were planted and parts of the understory were burned annually. The new habitat has seen the resurgence of rare pineland animals, including the red-cockaded woodpecker, which drills its nests into longleaf pine trees. Air Force conservationists have even drilled artificial nests into young pine trees to encourage the birds to nest (Coates et al., 2011).

On other bases in the US, the military has bought land surrounding bases, or struck deals with existing landowners, to create buffer zones between military activities and nearby civilian populations. This has had the effect both of creating better relationships with neighbouring towns, through protecting populations from noise pollution, and the creation of undisturbed habitat close to the base, but not actually on the base. This has sometimes led to relaxing of conservation rules on those bases, since similar habitat close by enjoys long-term protection (Cranston, 2019).

1.1.2 Crater as Habitat

Some wildlife actually benefits from the unusual environmental conditions sometimes found on a military base. The term “crater as habitat” was coined by Patrick Wright in a 1995 study on a village that was forcibly evacuated in Dorset, England, to make

way for tank training during World War II. It was never returned to its former inhabitants. Wright found that some creatures preferred to live in a military training area than a village (Wright, 1995). Correspondingly, the army training area on Salisbury Plain in southern England is popular with a number of endangered species, precisely because of some of the conditions that this type of land use brings. The rare marsh fritillary butterfly is attracted to the conditions on Salisbury Plain, with the training ground now home to 35% of the UK's population, as well as being the most important site for the butterfly in Northern Europe.

The secret of Salisbury Plain's attraction to the marsh fritillary is the abundance of a plant called the devil's bit scabious, on which marsh fritillary caterpillars like to feed. Devil's bit scabious grows well on land that gets burned periodically, which happens on Salisbury Plain thanks to occasional fires on firing ranges (Warren et al., 2007). Another creature that has used Salisbury's conditions to its advantage is the fairy shrimp. The puddles that form in the ditches and ruts created by the tracks left by heavy military vehicles are ideal habitat for this freshwater crustacean (Coates et al., 2011). In the USA, the endangered sonoran pronghorn antelope has chosen to make its home in high explosive target areas on some bases, most likely because of the increased growth rate of grasses and forbs in those environments after small fires clear away scrub (Warren et al., 2007).

1.1.3 Impacts of War

Active conflict poses the most risks to wildlife habitats, as opposed to training exercises or post-conflict recovery. War brings few benefits for flora or fauna (see Figure 1). Degradation of, for example, wetland habitats during fighting is both

incidental – due to damage done during the transport of equipment or the building of military camps – and intentional, thanks to damage carried out to meet military objectives. During the 1990–1994 Rwandan War, Akagera National Park, a conservation area in peacetime, saw wetland habitat degradation for three reasons: fighting and other military activities within the park; the halt of conservation work; and displaced populations being forced to poach and gather plants for food from within the park (Grimes et al, 2023).

Figure 1: The wide-ranging effects of military activity on the environment (Lawrence et al, 2015)

In their 2023 article 'Military activity and wetland-dependent wildlife: A warfare ecology perspective' in *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management*, Grimes et al recommend that conservation organizations become

involved as soon as conditions allow, to minimise the long-term negative impact on wetlands as early as possible in the post-conflict phase.

A journal article in *Environmental Management* the following year – ‘The Overlooked Contributors to Climate and Biodiversity Crises: Military Operations and Wars’ – suggested that the negative impact that military operations has had on both biodiversity and climate change throughout history may have been downplayed. Environmental impacts can be devastating, but the full picture is sometimes obscured due to national security concerns (Vuong, Nguyen, and La, 2024).

1.1.4 Rare Birds on Bases

Birds, in particular can fare well on military bases. In fact some birds do better on military land than anywhere else. The largest recorded breeding populations of both the black-capped vireo and the golden-cheeked warbler are found at the Fort Hood base in Texas. The two birds are rarely found together, as the vireo likes to nest in sparse landscapes of scrub oak and junipers, which can be created by military land disturbance, while the warbler prefers mature junipers. Fort Hood provides both (Warren et al., 2007). And in Hawaii, marines have doubled the population of the rare black-necked stilt with their manoeuvres of amphibious assault vehicles on mudflats, which break open dense areas of invasive plants to provide islands and moats that create ideal habitat for the birds to breed in (Warren et al. 2007).

It is worth noting that the Warren et al. 2007 study, Biodiversity and the Heterogeneous Disturbance Regime on Military Training Land, referenced above, was funded by the Installation Management Command (Europe Region) of the US Army and so tends to focus on the positive aspects of military bases for endangered species, rather than the negatives.

In spite of the information available about individual military bases and their contribution to biodiversity, little work has been done to assess the scale of khaki conservation globally (Zentelis and Lindenmayer, 2014). As mentioned earlier, there is currently no accurate data on the size of the global military-owned estate, let alone military conservation, but Australian academics Rick Zentelis and David Lindenmeyer estimate that at least 1% of the Earth's surface is owned by the armed forces, with the total likely to be more like 5-6% (2014).

1.1.4 Underneath the Spin: Compromises and Questionable Motives

There is no doubt that the US military's accommodation of endangered species on its land has been promoted as a good news story in instances where the military's presence may be less than palatable to local populations. The official line from military press offices and environmental departments is usually that environmental considerations do not impact training and that preserving biodiversity is almost always compatible with military land use. However, training area users and supervisors have been known to admit, when speaking anonymously, that taking into consideration the welfare of wildlife with conservation status can be a threat to the quality of training that can be provided (Lee Jenni et al., 2012).

Researchers from North Carolina State University found, in a 2012 study, that there was a considerable disconnect between the narrative provided by environmental management branches of the military and personnel on the ground involved with training exercises. One interviewee, straying somewhat from the official position, called the protected red-cockaded woodpecker his “own little version of bunnies and bugs from hell” adding that “they have the biggest impact on training lands here”. Another reported that if there was evidence of the red-cockaded woodpecker “in this one training area that we’re trying to train in, we can’t do it there”, adding that this increases training timelines (Lee Jenni et al., 2012, p.130).

In the United States, some disused military bases have been converted to wildlife refuges – a practice often dubbed “weapons to wildlife” (Coates et al., 2011). Such changes of land use often generate a blaze of positive publicity, with endangered species given a permanent sanctuary and local communities gaining the use of local countryside again, albeit with use sometimes restricted. However, communities don’t always want former villages repurposed as wildlife reserves after the military has left, they want the land back so it can be used the way it was before the military arrived (Davis, 2007). This has led to some academics questioning the true motives behind “weapons to wildlife” conversions. In 2007, University of Colorado academic David Havlick published a paper in *GeoJournal* looking at military to wildlife conversion sites in the US and examining whether the positive publicity around such schemes was always genuine. He suggested that since so much former military land has some level of contamination, from live munitions too numerous – or dangerous – to retrieve to residual effects of fuel spillage on water courses, that they are often unsuitable to be redeveloped for commercial or residential use. Enthusiastic

conversion to wildlife refuges is, therefore, often the only alternative to dereliction (Havlick, 2007).

Havlick (2007) notes that decision-makers have often explained the initiative to convert military land to wildlife refuges as being prompted by rare species having appeared unexpectedly and changing the course of the site's future. He suggests that this seems a little too convenient and that it happens surprisingly often. He uses the former base Rocky Mountain Arsenal as an example: "Federal officials at the Rocky Mountain Arsenal have at times exhibited a happy talent for discoveries for which they had not been searching. Thus we find the serendipitous account of the Rocky Mountain Arsenal's conversion to wildlife refuge: 'In a way, it was the eagles that made it happen' (US Fish and Wildlife Service, 1999, p. 5)" (Havlick, 2007, p.157). If Havlick's theory is correct, conversion of former military land to wildlife reserves could bring considerable savings – the clean-up cost of military related sites across the world is estimated to be more than \$500 billion (International Peace Bureau, 2002).

1.2 Energy Efficiency in the Armed Forces

As we have seen, a growing literature has examined the ecological value of military lands, documenting cases in which restricted access, periodic disturbance, and long-term land tenure have supported high levels of species richness. In parallel, policy-driven research has focused on improving energy efficiency, expanding renewable energy deployment, and reducing emissions from military infrastructure.

The 2010 US Air Force Energy Plan sets out steps for energy reduction and includes Space Force. The Air Force's own plans build on other DOD goals, including achieving zero net energy for all new facilities by the year 2030, which would see all of an installation's energy generated on the base (US Air Force, 2013). So US air bases, both at home and abroad, have been busily installing renewable energy sources as well as cutting deals to buy commercially produced renewable energy generated close by.

1.2.1 Solar and Wind Power installations

The challenges of installing solar and wind power infrastructure on a large scale are, of course, not specific to the US Space Force. A 2024 paper in *Wind Energy Science* recognised the dramatic increase in the proportion of energy generated by wind globally, but pointed to the difficulty of reliably maintaining supply–demand balance at an acceptable cost, as well as the challenges of integrating wind and solar technologies optimally (O'Malley and Holttinen et al, 2024).

Combining wind power with solar PV can help to contain variability and smooth out the uncertainty around supply. The advantages of combining these technologies in one plant revolve around shared transmission capacity and the reduced number of power electronics and controls. This can improve performance and the quality of the services provided to the power system at a lower cost (O'Malley and Holttinen et al, 2024).

1.2.2 European Initiatives

There is still a great deal of regional variation in wind power costs, compared to those of fossil fuels. Factors behind these variations include the amount of wind resource available locally, access to transmission, system costs, plant performance and productivity, operations and maintenance costs, financing arrangements, state tax incentives for renewables and fluctuations in coal and gas costs. Here, smaller countries sometimes fare better. For example, in Denmark, wind power provides more 50 per cent of the country's electricity on average, and up to 100 per cent at the windiest times of the year. Some European countries have targets of providing 80–100 per cent of energy annually from wind and solar PV (Holtinen, 2023).

There are many other innovations, particularly in Europe, that Space Force may be able to learn from. In 2017, the Spanish technology company Acciona won an award from a Spanish industry body for a wind plant that uses battery storage in Barásoain in Northern Spain. The installation uses two lithium-ion battery systems, with one providing 1 megawatt and 390 kilowatt-hours of power and the other 700 kilowatts and 700 kilowatt-hours of energy. Both batteries are connected to a 3-megawatt wind turbine (Deign, 2017). And the Barásoain plant is not unique. The Danish utility company Dong installed a 2-megawatt battery system in the same year at its 90-megawatt offshore wind farm in the Irish Sea (Deign, 2017).

These sorts of innovations could help bring USAF closer to its long-term goals for renewable energy and appear to have been envisaged in the Air Force Energy Strategic Plan. “The air base of the future would rely on power generated from renewable energy sources connected to a centralized storage facility and directly to

facilities. Excess power generated during the day or night from renewable sources would be stored and used during high demand periods, and the installation would rely on distributed sources of energy to reduce single point vulnerabilities and rely on energy from the main grid as backup – not the other way around” (US Air Force, 2013).

On the solar front, the Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory produces an annual report on the state of large-scale solar projects in the USA: *Utility-Scale Solar: Empirical Trends in Project Technology, Cost, Performance, and PPA Pricing in the United States*. The 2024 edition found that project costs for new photovoltaic (PV) installations are continuing to fall. Based on a 7.1 GWAC sample of 76 plants completed in 2023, costs have fallen by 75% since 2010, averaging 10 per cent annually. Seel and Kemp et al also found that solar’s combined value from wholesale electricity markets, climate damage reduction and public health outweighed generation costs and incentives considerably, yielding \$13.7 billion in net benefits in 2023 (Seel and Kemp et al, 2024, p.22).

1.2.3 Stepping Back from Renewables

A recent curve ball has been the Trump administration’s opposition to wind power of all kinds. Off-shore wind projects that have been hit the hardest, an example of which is Empire Wind, a 54-turbine project in the early stages of development off Long Island, New York that received a stop-work order from the Interior Department in April 2025. This was reversed after negotiations between state and federal officials, but significant economic damage was done. Shell and BP have now backed away

from investing in wind power in the US, following the cancellation of billions in federal funding for new wind power projects. EDF Group has cancelled plans to build a new wind farm off the New Jersey coast for up to 200 turbines. Though the cancellation of offshore wind farms may not directly impact USAF energy targets, the 50 per cent tariff that Trump has imposed on imported wind turbine parts will likely increase costs of future new wind power installations on military land (Lewis, 2024).

1.3 Research Gaps and Bias

Many of the studies available that look at biodiversity on military land were actually carried out by researchers employed by the military, which has obvious potential for bias. Studies contributed by the military are useful for in-depth case studies, as military personnel have year-round access to sites that civilian researchers may only be able to access briefly or not at all. However, they are unlikely to provide a full picture of biodiversity in a military context and often gloss over some of the more negative impacts of military activity on wildlife or plants. Thankfully, there have been more objective studies done by third parties over the years that can help to paint a more accurate picture.

When it comes to literature on energy efficiency on military bases, there is a smaller body of work on this. The military has much more prescriptive goals for energy efficiency than it does for biodiversity, so it needs to do its own detailed monitoring of energy efficiency for compliance purposes. And foreign governments sometimes require reporting of energy usage on US bases in their countries. But there is less interest from the wider research community about energy use on air bases, compared to the interest by academics in the conservation potential of military land.

However, as can be seen above, there is a great deal of research on renewable energy more widely that can easily be applied to military energy requirements.

1.4 Conclusion

This article identifies several critical gaps in the existing literature:

- A lack of integrated, quantitative models linking energy, emissions, and biodiversity in a military context
- Limited comparative analysis between military and non-military land
- Insufficient incorporation of ecological constraints into energy system planning for defense infrastructure
- Little exploration of trade-offs between short-term operational efficiency and long-term ecological resilience

Military installations occupy a unique position at the intersection of energy demand, environmental impact, and ecological opportunity. While existing research has generated valuable insights into both biodiversity conservation and energy efficiency on military lands, these literatures remain largely disconnected. By critically reviewing current knowledge and proposing an integrated systems-engineering framework, this dissertation will contribute a pathway toward more holistic assessment and decision-making in defense sustainability. Bridging these domains is essential not only for reducing environmental impacts, but also for enhancing the long-term resilience and adaptability of military infrastructure in an era of increasing environmental and geopolitical uncertainty.

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